

A STUDY OF LINGUISTIC ISSUES IN THE TRANSLATION OF THE NATIONAL-CULTURAL COMPONENT IN THE SENSE OF PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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Abstract: The article analyzes the cases of violation of the existing rules and norms when using phraseological units in oral and written speech. It also discusses the types of phraseological rules that exist and their place in speech.

Keywords: phraseology, language units, folklore, literary language, universality, semantic methods, language properties, expression.

The usage of phraseological units in speech, explain their usage according to national and cultural universality, differential and paradigmatic features, ways of transition from folklore to literary language, semantic properties, artistic and methodological possibilities, problems of translation in terms of form and meaning, compelling of a dictionary suitable for modern linguistics and the importance of covering their place in the national language. There is great interest to defining the specifics of phraseological units and their substantiation, their structural units, which are relevant to modern colloquial speech. However, the occurrence of slang, slang, dialectics, barbarism, archaisms in the phraseological units used in folklore is one of the most pressing theoretical issues. Phraseological units are grouped in a specific form, summarizing their methodological features and differing from each other in spoken and literary language.

Today's new reforms in our country, contribute to developing of language and culture. As our President noted: "Today, we are moving on the path of innovative development that aimed at radical renewal of all spheres of life of the state and society. After all, who will win in today's fast-paced world? Today our state based on new ideas, new ideas and innovations will win". The most effective reforms and innovations in the field of language and culture are an important factor for the analysis and study of the linguistic richness of our nation, as well as to increase the knowledge inherent in the phraseological units can be associated with the spiritual values of the nation.

The use of English and Uzbek phraseological units in linguistics has been studied to some extent. Further, the researches created by AA Izotova, AV Kunin on the theoretical foundations of English phraseology are of particular interest. Phraseological units, which are widely used in folklore and literary language, are a

peculiar feature of language. They have their own norms, regardless of whether they are used in a variety of forms in speech.

The existing normative makes it difficult for them to move from language to language. Terms are used in Uzbek linguistics with several different types of terms (phraseology), such as phraseology, phraseological unit, phraseological phrase, phraseological compound, fixed phrase, and phrase used as a synonym for each other. But there are those who call them as stable compounds. Regardless of the name of such linguistic units, they are the main subject of research in the Department of Phraseology in Linguistics. The section, which rounds out the system of phraseological units in linguistics, explores the specifics of phrases present in a language.

Phraseological units are made up of a combination of two or more language units, and their appearance is similar to word combinations. Sometimes there are such phraseologies and phrases that can be difficult to distinguish them as phrases and combinations. For example, the phrase "raise the hand" means denotative (own) when used in the process of physical training to raise the hand. If someone raises his hand to strike another, it has a connotative (portable) meaning. This example focuses on phrases are denotative and phraseologies are connotative and have to be distinguished from the context.

It was noted that the concept of phraseological norm has long existed in the language and speech in a clear exemplary form, adopted in that form, passed from mouth to mouth and always adhered to the "rule" of use, lexical-semantic, morphological-syntactic, stylistic-functional features. The lexical units need to be selected and used appropriately. If there are features contradicted the use of phraseological units, they deviate from the established norm or violate the norm. These cases are interpreted differently based on their types should be identified and justified.

Many scientists have distinguished deviations from the phraseological norm. Specially, V.A Svakovich, BS Schwartzkopf, Yu.A. Belchikov had given three types of deviations from the phraseological norm. These are:

Firstly, is the involuntary use of literary language units in speech without understanding the norm, even though it is not premeditated or deliberate;

Secondly, is the misinterpretation of language units in speech with correct comprehension and its analyses;

Thirdly, is the usual form of phraseological units in the process of speech, the expression of which is contrary to their structural rules and internal system;

All in all, The existence of knowledge, norms and rules related to phraseology can be understood when they are applied in the context not in their own way, as in the traditional pattern that is passed from generation to generation, word of mouth, but

incompletely or distorted. It should be noted that in the event of deviations from the norms of the use of phraseological units, it takes permissible to evaluate and interpret them correctly in speech.

Phraseological units that exist should be widely used in works of all genres, should be standardized in order to be used as one of the effective means of communication, increasing the aesthetic expression of the word between the protagonists of the work.

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